

Analysis of Logistic Supportability for Complex Systems

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Key Words: Supportability, Provisioning, Network Availability

ABSTRACT	ASSEMBLAGE	FUNCTION
<p>This paper describes a methodology for evaluating the logistical supportability of complex systems. Specifically, this paper addresses the supportability of the Army's Mobile Subscriber Equipment (MSE). Mobile Subscriber Equipment represents a prime example of a complex military system which employs many Continuity of Operations (CONOPS) features (i.e. system networking, component redundancy, and functional bypass capabilities).</p> <p>The Mobile Subscriber Equipment Supportability Analysis determined that the additional procurement of specific spare parts could greatly increase MSE performance. The MSE Analysis provided a means to increase the expected Call Completion Rate of the Army's primary corps and division common user voice communication system significantly. The increased cost associated with acquiring the additional spares was virtually negligible when compared to the MSE procurement cost.</p>	<p>System Control Center (SCC)</p> <p>Node Central Switch (NCS)</p> <p>Large Extension Node (LEN)</p> <p>Small Extension Node (SEN)</p> <p>Mobile Subscriber Radiotelephone Terminal (MSRT)</p> <p>Radio Access Unit (RAU)</p> <p>Line-of-Sight Radio (LOS)</p> <p>Digital Non-Secure Voice Telephone (DNVT)</p>	<p>Configures, Reconfigures and Monitors Network Operations</p> <p>Serves as both a Tandem Switch as well as an Access Point for RAUs and Extension Nodes</p> <p>Provides Interfaces to Combat Net Radio, Commercial, and other Service and Tactical Satellite Equipment</p> <p>Provides Access to MSE Network, for either Digital Secure or Non-Secure Voice Communications</p> <p>Permits Mobile Users to Communicate Secure Voice, Facsimile, and Data Traffic on a Discrete Address Basis</p> <p>Provides MSRTs User Access to the MSE Common User Switchboard Network</p> <p>Provides Radio Transmission Capability Between Various Network Elements</p> <p>Provides Voice, Data, and Facsimile Access to the MSE Network</p>

INTRODUCTION

The complexity of military weapon systems increases each year. A major challenge placed upon the Department of Defense is fielding weapon systems which are logistically supportable. Methodologies are required to insure that the soldier can support his/her equipment in an efficient and cost effective manner.

Continuity of operations (CONOPS) features are a major contributor to the growing complexity of defense systems. CONOPS features improve system performance by allowing for graceful degradation in the event of a failure. Examples of CONOPS features are system networking, component redundancy, and functional bypass capabilities. No single methodology currently exists to evaluate the impact of provisioning on the performance of complex systems containing CONOPS features; however, tools exist which can be combined to form an effective tool for determining provisioning needs.

BACKGROUND

The Army's Mobile Subscriber Equipment represents a prime example of a military system which employs all of the CONOPS features listed above for which a logistical supportability analysis was performed. Mobile Subscriber Equipment is an area communications network intended for use by the Army from corps down to unit level. The network includes both mobile (i.e. radiotelephone) users as well as wire line subscribers arranged in a nodal system which integrates microwave radio trunking, automatic tandem and local switching, COMSEC, and system control, with user owned input/output equipment. The MSE network consists of eight different types of assemblages as shown in figure 1.

FIGURE 1. MSE Assemblages

The backbone of the MSE network is the collection of Node Central Switches linked to one another via Line-of-Sight Radios. The backbone provides a medium through which calls are routed by the best available path. A call enters the backbone through either a SEN, LEN, or RAU. A subscriber may originate a call from either a MSRT or a DNVT. DNVT calls will enter the backbone through either a SEN or a LEN. MSRT originated calls will access the backbone through a RAU. The connectivity for a division is shown in figure 2.

FIGURE 2. MSE Connectivity

As previously stated, MSE possesses several CONOPS capabilities. Two of the MSE CONOPS capabilities are Essential-User Bypass (EUB) and Nodal Reaffiliation. Essential-User Bypass allows calls to proceed into the backbone through an NCS, even if a portion of the NCS has failed. The data base residing on the NCS with which a subscriber is affiliated is also stored within an adjacent NCS; therefore, when calls are unable to be processed by the designated NCS the call may still be forwarded using the adjacent NCS's data base. However, not all MSE subscribers have Essential-User Bypass capability. The second MSE CONOPS feature, Nodal Reaffiliation, allows nodes to affiliate with an alternate functional node should the currently affiliated node fail. Most nodes reaffiliate by rehomeing their Line-of-Sight Radio.

MSE will be deployed throughout the Army. A typical five division corps will contain a backbone of 42 Node Central Switches. Access to the corps backbone will be obtained through 224 SENs, 9 LENs, and 80 RAUs. The 80 RAUs will support approximately 1900 MSRTs with the SENs and LENs supporting approximately 5500 DNVTs.

ANALYSIS

Methodology

Four previously available models were used to perform the MSE supportability analysis. The Selected Essential-Item Stockage for Availability Method (SESAME) model was used to compute the operational availability of each of the major system assemblages. Redundant parts contained in the assemblages were evaluated by determining their criticality in terms of passing a single call through the assemblage. Those parts which were not dedicated to passing a given call were not allowed to impact the assemblage operational availability.

A measure other than operational availability was necessary to assess the impact of logistics on the overall system. The system characteristic chosen to represent MSE was the probability of completing a single call (P_{sc}) between any two random points in the MSE network. Two models were used to evaluate the P_{sc} for MSE. First, a model which plays the central nodal portion of the system was used to determine the probability that enough equipment is available, considering reliability and logistics only, to pass a single call through the backbone. Second, a spreadsheet-type model which addresses all the possible path types through the system, and assigns appropriate weights to each path, was used to determine an overall probability of completing that single call.

Where appropriate these last two models were modified to account for hardware and functional redundancy available within the system which would affect the probability of call completion. Finally, the Mobile Subscriber Equipment Simulation (MOSES) was run using assemblage availabilities to take into account the effect of such influences as traffic contention and topography on the probability of completing a call.

Assemblage Operational Availability (Ao)

The Selected Essential-Item Stockage for Availability Method (SESAME) model was used to determine the expected Ao for each assemblage type for both peacetime and wartime operating tempos. SESAME will calculate the expected steady-state operational availability for a piece of equipment given the equipment's provisioning, component failure rates, supply support structure, and associated supply support performance. Some of the key SESAME data inputs for MSE are shown in figure 3.

- Order and Ship Time for
- Part at Contractor Regional Facility or Army GS 7 days
 - Part at Contractor or Army Depot 21 days
- Wholesale Fill Rate 85%
- Delay if no part at Contractor or Army Depot 120 days
- No-Evidence-of-Failure Rate 20%

FIGURE 3. SESAME Inputs

Many of the MSE Line Replaceable Units (LRUs) were excluded from the initial SESAME analysis. This reduction in the number of LRUs was performed to eliminate all but "Call-Essential" LRUs, (i.e., those LRUs necessary to complete a single call). The list of "Call-Essential" LRUs for each assemblage was provided by the MSE prime contractor. The comparison between the number of different LRUs in each assemblage and the corresponding number of "Call-Essential" LRUs in each assemblage is shown in figure 4.

LRU	TOTAL	CALL ESSENTIAL
DNVT	2	2
LEN	207	83
LOS	58	28
MSRT	39	39
NCS	198	74
RAU	76	15
SEN	71	26

FIGURE 4. Call-Essential LRUs

Network Modeling

Three models were used to determine the impact of provisioning on network performance. The first of these models, the Backbone Trunking Model, determines the probability of completing a call through the backbone trunking system (Figure 5). The circles in Figure 5 represent Node Central Switches connected by Line-of-Sight Radios. The model simulates calls being placed upon the backbone one at a time, with the origin and destination of each call being chosen randomly. If a call entering the backbone through point A has any available path to exit through point B, the call is labeled a success. The probability of completing a single call through the backbone is determined by the number of successful calls divided by the total number of calls placed.

FIGURE 5. Backbone Trunking Model

Essential-User Bypass was modeled by not allowing the failure of bypassable LRUs to impact the Ao of the Node Central Switches. The Backbone Trunking Model was run using both the Ao for a NCS which could be bypassed and the Ao for a NCS given a subscriber does not have Essential-User Bypass capability. The two results provide a bound on the probability of completing a call through the backbone.

The second network model, the Probability of Completing a Single Call (Psc) Model, calculates the percent of all calls placed on the MSE network that will be successfully completed. There are 27 unique call paths through the MSE network (see figure 6). The Psc of each of these paths is the product of the Psc of each assemblage residing on the given unique path. The backbone Psc, determined using the Backbone Trunking Model, is entered into each path as shown in figure 6. The Psc of each of the 27 unique paths is weighted based upon the number of occurrences of each path type in the MSE network. The Psc for the MSE network is the sum of the 27 weighted path Psc.

FIGURE 6. Probability of Completing a Single Call Model

Reaffiliation was modeled by bounding the MSE system Psc between 0% reaffiliation capability and 100% instantaneous reaffiliation. 100% instantaneous reaffiliation was calculated by letting the Ao of the Backbone, RAU, and LOS radios equal 100% (i.e. during a failure of these portions of the network, subscribers could reaffiliate to the backbone through alternate paths).

The third and final network model, MOSES, determines the User Grade-of-Service (UGOS) and Call Completion Rate (CCR) provided by MSE. UGOS and CCR are both measures of system performance. UGOS is the percent of all calls which reach their destination, where a busy signal at the receiving end counts as a failed call. CCR is the percent of all calls which reach their destination, where a busy signal at the receiving end counts as a success. The impact of logistics and reliability on system performance was incorporated into the MOSES model by eliminating the number of each type of assemblage expected to be unavailable during the period addressed by the simulation, where assemblage unavailability was determined directly from SESAME.

MOSES inherently plays MSRT reaffiliation. Complete reaffiliation of other nodes as well as 100% Essential-User Bypass capability was incorporated into the simulation by setting the NCS Ao = 100%. Running MOSES with both the NCS Ao = 100% and NCS Ao = SESAME output, provided a bound for the MSE UGOS and CCR.

RESULTS

Probability of Completing a Single Call

Figure 7 shows the type of results that could be expected for the MSE network peacetime Psc as a function of both Essential-User Bypass and Nodal Reaffiliation. In this example, the MSE peacetime probability of completing a single call, given that only one transmitting and one receiving subscriber are using the network at any given time, lies between 94% and 98%.

Note: The results depicted in Figure 7 are intended to provide an example of the type of results obtained from the MSE supportability analysis.

FIGURE 7. Probability of Completing a Single Call

Call Completion Rate and User Grade-of-Service

Using the SESAME Model results as inputs, MOSES computed the Call Completion Rate and User Grade-of-Service for the MSE network during wartime. Figure 8 shows the CCR and UGOS baseline which is the expected wartime performance of MSE given that there are no nodal failures. Figure 8 also shows the impact of reliability and logistics on system performance.

	BASELINE (NO NODAL FAILURES)	CURRENT PROVISIONING
CALL COMPLETION RATE	96%	82%
USER GRADE-OF-SERVICE	88%	79%

Note: These numbers did not result from the MSE Supportability Analysis. The results shown are intended only as an example to show the relative differences between the baseline case and the expected performance based upon current provisioning.

Figure 8. MOSES Results

Improvements

SESAME was used to determine the additional provisioning cost associated with improving each of the assemblage operational availabilities. Various combinations of increased sparing levels were assessed for each of the assemblages resulting in a near optimum set of required additional spares. The cost of the additional spares was \$21,000 per Signal Battalion. MOSES was used to evaluate the increase in MSE performance based upon the additional provisioning. The MOSES results are tabulated for both current and increased provisioning in Figure 9.

	CURRENT PROVISIONING (\$0/SIG Bn)	INCREASED PROVISIONING (\$21K/SIG Bn)
CALL COMPLETION RATE	82%	89%
USER GRADE-OF-SERVICE	79%	84%

Note: These numbers did not result from the MSE Supportability Analysis. They are intended only as an example to show the relative impact of increased provisioning.

FIGURE 9. Improved Sparing

Many of the MSE Line Replaceable Units were not included in the above system level analysis since they were Non-Call-Essential. However, these Non-Call-Essential LRUs are still important in that their failure may degrade MSE functionality. SESAME was utilized to determine the operational availability for each Non-Call-Essential LRU. The cost associated with increased provisioning for these LRUs amounted to \$142,000 per Signal Battalion. Therefore, the total cost associated with increased provisioning for MSE was \$163,000 per Signal Battalion.

SUMMARY

The Mobile Subscriber Equipment Supportability Analysis determined that the additional procurement of specific spare parts could greatly increase MSE performance. The MSE Analysis provided a means to increase the expected Call Completion Rate of the Army's primary corps and division common user voice communication system significantly. The increased cost associated with acquiring the additional spares was virtually negligible when compared to the total MSE procurement cost.

BIOGRAPHY

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Mr. Mortin has been an Aerospace Engineer at the Army Materiel Systems Analysis Activity since 1987. He graduated from the State University of New York at Buffalo with a B.S. degree in Aerospace Engineering in 1986. Mr. Mortin then graduated from the Army's School of Engineering and Logistics Maintainability Engineering Program in 1987. Mr. Mortin is currently working towards a M.S. in Statistics from the University of Delaware.

Mr. Mortin has received awards for both his work on the Army's Mobile Subscriber Equipment and AH-64 (Apache) Helicopter. He is also the recipient of an Honorable Mention Award from the Baltimore Federal Executive Board as the Outstanding Scientific/Technical Professional.